

OSC15
speaker

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What can and what should future laboratory experiments contribute to our knowledge about the mechanisms of air-sea gas transfer?

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Laboratory experiments in wind/wave facilities offer the chance to study the air-sea gas transfer under controllable conditions (e.g., Jähne *et al.*, 1987). In the 70s to 90s a lot of laboratory experiments have been performed. They brought a wealth of results but ultimately failed to develop a comprehensive model explaining air-sea gas transfer and to develop a parameterisation that can be applied to the field. Then the focus of research shifted to field experiments and to find empirical relations between the gas transfer velocity and wind speed.

In the last decade, however, experiments in wind/wave facilities have seen a revival. This is due to two reasons. Firstly, new facilities are available with properties to run experiments that could not be done before. One of them is the Heidelberg Aeolotron, a large annular facility featuring unlimited fetch conditions with the built-up of large waves. It is gas tight and chemically clean and can be used with deionised water and seawater. Because of the annular geometry and water cleaning devices, it is ideally suited to perform measurements with various types of surface active material. More recently, hurricane force wind/wave facilities became available, which can be operated at wind speeds up to three times higher than previous facilities. The first facility of this kind is the fresh water Kyoto high wind speed facility (Iwano *et al.*, 2013; Krall and Jähne, 2014). A second much larger facility of this kind operated with seawater just became operational at the RSMAS in Miami, Florida, the Surge-Structure-Atmosphere-Interaction facility (SUSTAIN, <http://www.rsmas.miami.edu/seawater>). Secondly, new experimental techniques have become available. Most noteworthy are the various types of mass spectrometric techniques, which can be used to perform simultaneous gas exchange experiments with many gas tracers (Mesarchaki *et al.*, 2014).

▲ Figure 1: The annular Heidelberg air sea interaction facility, Aeolotron, video available at <http://tinyurl.com/aeolotronH>

Only contact-less imaging techniques can give a direct insight into the processes controlling air-sea gas exchange. Flow visualisation techniques have a long tradition and have been used extensively in wind-wave facilities, e.g., Turney and Banerjee (2013), although it is still difficult to resolve the flow field within the viscous boundary layer and to apply 3-D flow visualisation techniques. In order to reveal the mechanisms of air-sea gas transfer, it is also necessary to image all other parameters involved. This includes short wind waves and most importantly concentration field within the aqueous mass boundary layer. Significant progress has been made with both parameters recently. Kiefhaber *et al.*, (2014) introduced a high-speed wave-slope imaging system and Kräuter *et al.* (2014) a fluorescence technique to visualise the thickness of the mass boundary layer. All these techniques cannot be applied in the field, only in wind/wave facilities. The only exception is active thermography (Nagel *et al.*, 2015). It can be applied both in the

lab and the field and thus provides an important link between field and laboratory experiments. This technique is not only capable to measure the gas transfer velocity with a temporal resolution of a few minutes. Because the water surface temperature is imaged under the condition of a constant heat flux, it gives also direct insight into the turbulence structure at the water surface.

Given the significant progress in experimental techniques, it can be expected that experiments in the new wind/wave facilities will make a significant contribution to the understanding of air-sea gas transfer and other small-scale air-sea interaction processes. Such experiments can now cover gas tracers with the full range of solubility and diffusion coefficients occurring in the environment. The structure of the near-surface turbulence and the influence of the surface micro layer and natural surfactants can be studied. And the high wind speed range can finally be explored in the laboratory to separate the different mechanisms contributing to the high gas transfer velocities in this regime.

▲ **Figure 2:** The Kyoto high-wind speed facility, video available at <http://tinyurl.com/H-Wind-Kyoto>

A first experiment of this kind took place within the joint BMBF project SOPRAN in the Heidelberg Aeolotron in November 2014 to study the influence of the surface micro layer on air-sea gas exchange in natural seawater. Results from this experiment will be reported with several contributions at the SOLAS Open Science Conference in Kiel this year.

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Climate and Ocean: Variability, Predictability and Change

Over the past year, CLIVAR has been developing its new structure that includes the Research Foci activities. Last November in Moscow, plans of all Research Foci (<http://www.clivar.org/about/research-foci>) were presented to the CLIVAR Scientific Steering Group (SSG) for approval before starting activities. Four of those plans were considered in a mature stage and received SSG's endorsement: 'Regional sea level change and coastal impacts', 'Consistency between planetary energy balance and ocean heat storage', 'Decadal climate variability and predictability' and 'ENSO in a changing climate'. The groups leading these Research Foci will now begin implementing their activities. The SSG felt that two of the Research Foci plans needed to be further developed. The 'Marine biophysical interactions and dynamics of upwelling systems' Research Focus team is organising a planning workshop with invited experts that will help in further identifying scientific gaps and potential ways forward for rapid development of new knowledge in those regions. The 'Intraseasonal, seasonal and interannual variability and predictability of monsoon systems' Research Focus team will discuss their plans with the newly established CLIVAR/GEWEX (Global Energy and Water Exchanges Project) monsoons panel. Another recently formed core panel within CLIVAR is the climate dynamics panel. Its overarching objective is to advance our basic understanding of atmosphere-ocean climate dynamics using observations and models and to determine the role of climate dynamics in shaping climate variability and change on seasonal to centennial time scales with a special focus on the role of the ocean.

One of the main CLIVAR activities for the coming year will be the organisation of the CLIVAR Open Science Conference (OSC2016), which is planned for September 2016 in Qingdao, China, pending official government approval. The CLIVAR OSC2016 will bring leaders of the international climate community together to discuss the state of the science, prioritise plans for the future, and initiate new collaborations, and to engage scientists from different disciplines.

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